

The EVANS program: a French-Czech collaboration for the improvement of the neutronics safety of VVER-1000 reactors

R. Henry^{1,*}, M. Cheikh², P. Blaise², M. Zilly¹, F. Brijar³, T. Czako³, T. Peltan³, B. Miglierini¹, J. Plancher²

¹Framatome, Erlangen, Germany; ²Framatome, France; ³Centrum výzkumu Řež, Husinec, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

The Experimental Validation of Advanced Neutronics Codes for Safety (EVANS) project is a collaborative scientific initiative between the Czech Republic and France. Its aim is the generation of new experimental data to enhance the safety of VVER-1000 reactors as well as other PWR type of reactors. This three-year project is partially funded by the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic and the French National Research Agency. The paper describes the experimental program to be performed at the LR-0 zero power reactor operated by Centrum výzkumu Řež. Two specific effects relevant to nuclear safety are investigated: local over moderation caused by assembly bowing and local void effect. These experiments are expected to provide unique data to support advanced neutronics studies for VVER core safety. Preliminary results are presented for the experimental design study as well as the initial analysis of the local over moderation experiment, using the reference Monte-Carlo code Serpent and the deterministic code APOLLO3.

Keywords: neutronics, safety, VVER-1000, APOLLO3, Serpent

1. INTRODUCTION

A comprehensive safety and reliability assessment of existing nuclear power plants requires advanced expertise to analyze severe accident scenarios. This goal is achieved through extensive experimental benchmark data from research reactors and corresponding code validation studies. France and the Czech Republic are collaborating to enhance the safety analysis and operational performance of their Light Water Reactor (LWR) fleets, with a particular—though not exclusive—focus on VVER-1000 reactors [1]. Previous collaborations, such as the European CamiVVER program, have already produced significant databases and feedback to improve LWR safety and performance [2].

Within a joint initiative supported by the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic (TACR) and the French National Research Agency (ANR), Framatome and its long-standing Czech partners at Centrum výzkumu Řež (CVR) as well as UJV Řež have developed a dedicated experimental program: the EVANS project. This project encompasses both neutronics and thermal-hydraulics, aiming to establish experimental benchmarks for validating nuclear transport codes for power reactors—especially, but not limited to, VVER types. The ultimate objective is to further enhance the safe, robust, and economical operation of nuclear power plants.

Building on the achievements of the CamiVVER program, EVANS will extend validation efforts to previously unmeasured experimental scenarios, providing valuable and unique data to the neutronics community.

The paper begins by presenting the context and objectives of the project. It then thoroughly describes the experimental campaigns. Subsequent sections provide an overview of work packages (WP) 1 and 4. The Serpent [3] design study, used to tailor the water-gap experiment, is described first, followed by a preliminary comparison between APOLLO3 [4] and Serpent. The conclusion highlights the project's future steps.

* corresponding author: romain.henry@framatome.com

2. CONTEXT AND OBJECTIVES

2.1. Context

The core objective of the EVANS project is the experimental investigation of key physical phenomena occurring within nuclear reactor cores. In particular, non-uniform water gaps between fuel assemblies and local coolant density variations—such as those associated with the void coefficient—significantly affect safety parameters like power distribution and reactivity. The project aims to develop experimental benchmarks and validate nuclear transport codes for power reactors, with a primary focus on VVER units, to further enhance safe, robust, and economical reactor operation.

This innovative benchmark targets state-of-the-art computational codes used in the French and Czech nuclear industries, as well as advanced experimental research devices, to accurately assess the impact of core inhomogeneities, specifically:

- Enlarged water gaps between fuel assemblies (expanded inter-assembly gaps)
- Fuel assembly voiding (simulated by replacement of moderator by aluminum)

Both phenomena may arise during off normal or severe accident scenarios and can directly influence reactor safety. Improving the understanding of these effects through experimental studies and advanced simulations is therefore essential. Currently, these scenarios are addressed using highly conservative assumptions, which can restrict efficient and economical reactor operation.

The backbone of the project is the LR-0 zero-power reactor [5], operated by CVR in the Czech Republic. Within the EVANS project, VVER-1000 core mock-ups featuring increased water gaps and voided assemblies will be constructed and thoroughly characterized in terms of reactivity and power distribution. Nuclear transport codes will guide the design of experimental setups at LR-0. Following reactor tests, experimental benchmark results will be systematically compared with computational predictions, enabling quantification of discrepancies and identification of areas for improvement in calculation methods and nuclear data.

2.2. Scientific program and overall project structure

The EVANS project is organized into five work packages (WPs), with the scientific program comprising an analytical component (WP1, WP4, and WP5) and an experimental component (WP2 and WP3). The structure of the EVANS project is illustrated in Figure 1:

Figure 1. Work packages organisation of EVANS, including TH work

The paper gives an overview of the experimental campaign and mainly focuses on the neutronics part of the collaboration.

2.3. The neutronics experimental program

The EVANS project consists of two distinct experimental phases: the analysis of local over moderation and the assessment of full void effects. Both configurations are investigated using a dedicated seven-assembly geometry, which serves as a reference model for evaluating reactivity changes and local pin-by-pin power perturbations. Detailed descriptions of these experimental setups are provided in the following paragraphs.

Figure 2. Serpent 2 model of the core for water gap experiment (left) and void experiment (right).

The experimental core design calculations are performed by CVR using the MCNP code [6], which also supports the criticality analyses required before conducting the experiments. In parallel, Framatome conducts equivalent calculations with the Serpent code.

2.3.1. Water gap experiment

The water gap experiment aims to study the impact of a local over moderation on both reactivity and pin-by-pin fission rate distributions. The configuration is meant to improve calculation schemes in case of potential bowing effect, and in particular, the precise modeling of self-shielding and mesh refinement to be used with MoC (method of characteristics) embarked in the APOLLO3 deterministic transport code.

The over moderation will be highly dissymmetrical, by displacing a peripheral assembly of the reference geometry. The following assembly arrangements are planned:

The reference configuration is composed of seven 2%-enriched UO_2 VVER-1000 assemblies in regular geometry (236 mm pitch). The criticality is obtained by adequate water height.

One assembly at the periphery is slightly displaced away from the central assembly, hence increasing the local water gap.

Figure 2 shows 7 fuel assemblies with fuel constant enrichment 2.0 wt.% in regular VVER-1000 lattice geometry. Fuel assembly lattice pitch is 236 mm and spacer grid flat-to-flat dimension 234 mm. Figure 2 also shows six dry tubes for the control system instrumentation. The critical moderator (pure demineralized water) level for the reference unperturbed configuration was determined within 1983 critical experiment [5] as 617.6 mm (moderator level is measured from the bottom of the fissile column). The perturbation induced by the water gap increase will be controlled by an ad hoc adaptation of the critical water level (H_{cr}).

The assembly bowing effect will be evaluated from the activity of the irradiated fuel pins and their changes when the inter-assembly gap is increased. To ensure a balance between acceptable dead time and sufficient activity level, a maximum of 24 pins can be measured in one irradiation on the LR-0 reactor. This limit has been determined to ensure that the activity of the last pin being measured remains adequate, considering its half-life.

Pins that are most significant for determining the spatial distribution of power will be selected for activity measurement, which will be realized in the area corresponding to the neutron flux maximum ($H_{cr}/2$). The limited number of pins measured in a single exposure requires repeating the exposure in the same experimental parameters. Normalization is performed using a special current ionization detector (gamma compensated chamber KNK-56).

2.3.2. 3D void experiment

The second experimental phase corresponds to the 100% void experiment. To our knowledge, this kind of configuration has only been studied for PWR situations **Error! Reference source not found..** It then constitutes a first-of-a-kind for VVER-1000 applications. Such scenario can occur in case of LOCA (Loss Of Coolant Accident) or boiling of the coolant.

The following assembly arrangements are planned:

- 7 VVER-1000 assemblies in regular geometry (236 mm pitch) will serve as a new reference configuration: the central 2%-enriched UO_2 assembly is surrounded by 6 (six) 3%-enriched UO_2 assemblies, in order to ensure sufficient reactivity reserve to compensate for high void fraction negative effect. Figure 2 (right) reproduces the reference 7-assemblies for void analysis.
- The central assembly will be voided using hollowed aluminum (Al) blocks specially manufactured for the purpose of the experiment. These blocks will be piled up around the fuel pins to locally reproduce an almost 100% void along the full assembly axis. Figure 3 reproduces a CAD view of the expected configuration
- A potential intermediate configuration could be a partially axially voided central assembly, which could reproduce the increase in a void bubble at the core bottom. This would require a full 3D analysis.

Figure 3. CAD simulation of the Al-blocks to be inserted in the central assembly.

As for the water gap experimental phase, the measurements will include both reactivity effects, by adapting water height to the loss of reactivity induced by increased void fraction, completed by several

local radial pin-by-pin fission rate distributions in the voided plan. Special attention will be on the water/void interface.

The feasibility of AI-blocks is currently under investigation.

The next section gives some insight on the WP1. It presents the calculation design for the WG experiment.

3. Experimental campaign A: non-uniform inter-assembly WG, design calculation

3.1. Codes and methods

Accurate modelling of the complex geometry of the LR-0 requires the use of reference Monte-Carlo codes. The nuclear data used by each participant is the ENDF/B-VIII.0 library.

The calculations performed at Framatome were obtained with the Serpent version 2.2.1. To reduce the statistical uncertainty to an acceptable level, 1000 cycles of 10^6 neutrons were simulated. Before that, 50 inactive cycles were performed to ensure the convergence of the fission sources (this number was determined through an entropy study of the fission source). In terms of multiplication factor, the statistical uncertainty is less than 4 pcm. Fission rates have a maximum statistical uncertainty below 0.05 %.

For this first experiment, it was decided to start from a homogeneous core of 7 fuel assemblies (FAs) enriched to 2 weight percent (w%) ^{235}U (Figure 2). Increasing the water gap (WG) results in an increase in the moderation, and thus increases core reactivity.

The level of water for the nominal configuration is 61.5 cm. During the experiment, the water level will be different for the WG case, but it was kept constant for the design study.

3.2. Determination of the Water-gap size

The first step in designing this experiment was to determine the WG size. To do so, the upper FA was moved along the y-axis millimeter by millimeter. Figure 4 shows the reactivity increase caused by WG expansion.

It can be seen that optimal moderation occurs around 8 mm. This value was chosen to maximize perturbation in pin fission rate distribution.

Figure 4. Reactivity evolution with respect to the deviation to nominal WG

3.3. Selection of the pin for the irradiation campaign

The second step was to determine the pin positions for measurement. To guide this decision, the fission rate difference between the nominal and 8 mm WG was visualized. Figure 5 shows the relative increase in the fission rate of the pins near the WG.

Figure 5. pin-by-pin fission rate effect of a 8mm water gap increase (Serpent simulation)

Based on the study, 56 positions (Figure 6) were selected. Among them, 11 pairs of symmetric positions were selected to detect any asymmetry in the core. A normalization pin was also selected and will be present in every irradiation cycle.

Figure 6. Selection of the pin for the measurement

Five irradiation cycles will be performed. Each cycle will measure the activity of 11 pins plus the normalization pin, for both the nominal and 8 mm WG configurations.

4. WP4 APOLLO3 comparison with SERPENT2

Some preliminary 2D APOLLO3 calculations were performed by Framatome on the reference configuration. JEFF3.1.1 nuclear data base is used for APOLLO3.

4.1. Multiplication factor

To consider axial leakages, 2D APOLLO3 calculations were performed using an imposed axial buckling. This axial buckling is deduced from Serpent calculations. The core height is divided in 10 equal zones, that can be seen as detectors, in which fission rates are calculated for each assembly. From fission rates per assembly and per zone, a mean fission rate per zone is calculated for the whole core. Results are presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Mean axial fission rates deduced from Serpent calculations

From these results, the axial buckling is deduced by comparing axial fission rates distribution from 0 to critical water level (61.5cm) with a sinus function. Comparison gives an axial buckling of 0.0025cm^{-2} . With this axial buckling, the APOLLO3 multiplication factor is 1.00040, corresponding to a deviation of 92 pcm relative to the Serpent reference (multiplication factor is 0.99948).

4.2. Pin fission rates

Pin fission rates were computed with the APOLLO3 deterministic code and compared to the Serpent Monte-Carlo results. Figure 8 illustrates the comparison.

Comparisons show a very good agreement between the two codes. For most pins, the absolute deviation remains below 0.5%.

Some peripheral pins have relatively higher discrepancy due to the size of the water surrounding the core and due to the reflective boundary conditions. Figure 8 also shows the geometry used for the APOLLO3 calculations. The fuel assemblies are closer to the box sides than in the Serpent reference, so radial leakages are underestimated and so fission rates on peripheral fuel pins are overestimated. A bigger box will be considered for the continuation of the project.

Figure 8: Pin fission rate discrepancy between APOLLO3 and Serpent on the reference configuration (left) and APOLLO3 model for the reference core for water gap experiment (right)

5. CONCLUSIONS

The EVANS project is a French-Czech collaboration to generate new experimental data for improving the safety of VVER-1000 reactors as well as PWR type of reactors. It focuses on experimental benchmarks and code validation for advanced neutronics and thermal-hydraulics. The project is structured into five work packages, combining analytical and experimental components. The project will provide unique experimental data for VVER-1000 safety analysis and supports the validation of advanced computational codes. In this paper an overview of the neutronics program was given (design study, preliminary analysis etc.). Future work will include the analysis of the measured pin-by-pin fission rate, comparison with the numerical prediction and refinement of the models.

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